

IL-6

INTEGRATIVE MOLECULAR RECOGNITION APPROACHES TO DECODE GLYCAN-PROTEIN INTERACTIONS

Filipa Marcelo^{a,b}

^aApplied Molecular Biosciences Unit, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal; ^bAssociate Laboratory i4HB, Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal

e-mail: filipa.marcelo@fct.unl.pt

Keywords: Tumor-glycans, MGL, anti-sTn antibody, NMR, Molecular modeling, X-Ray crystallography

Abnormal mucin O-glycosylation signature is a common feature of cancer that yields tumor-associated mucin O-glycans.^[1] Among others, Tn- (GalNAc α 1-O-Ser/Thr) and its sialylated form, the sTn-antigen (Neu5Ac α 2-6GalNAc α 1-O-Ser/Thr), are tumor-associated mucin O-glycans exclusively exposed in cancers cells.

Tn- and sTn-antigens interact with lectins enrolled in tumor immune surveillance and this recognition process has been identified to dampen anti-tumor immune responses.^[2] Specifically, the macrophage galactose-type lectin (MGL) expressed by immune cells binds these tumor-glycans^[3] and mediate anti-tumor immune suppression.^[4] In this perspective, molecules able to interfere with the aberrant MGL/tumor-glycans interactions axis could have the potential to modulate MGL-induced anti-tumor immunity for immunomodulation strategies in cancer.

Additionally, sTn-antigen is a promising target for therapeutic and diagnostic applications and for that purpose research efforts have been devoted to developing anti-sTn antibodies.^[5,6] However, the enhancement of the specificity of anti-sTn antibodies is of paramount importance for their use as tumor immunotherapeutic or/and diagnostic applications.

To rationally design new and alternative glycan-based anti-cancer therapies is essential to have a detailed knowledge of the molecular recognition process of the tumor-glycans by immune related glycan binding proteins, as MGL and anti-sTn antibodies. In this context, through an integrative and multidisciplinary approach that includes chemical synthesis, molecular biology, molecular modeling, biophysical and structural based techniques, with special focus in NMR-based binding methods, the molecular basis of tumour-glycans/glycomimetics recognition by human MGL^[7,8,9] and an anti-sTn antibody will be described.

References

- [1] S. S. Pinho, C. A. Reis. *Nat Rev Cancer*. **2015**, 15, 540-555.
- [2] E. Rodríguez, et al *Nat Rev Immunol*. **2018**, 18, 204–211.
- [3] F. Marcelo, et al. *J Biol Chem.*, **2019**, 294, 1300-1311.
- [4] K. Lenos, et al. *Oncotarget*. **2015**, 6, 26278–26290.
- [5] L. R. Loureiro et al. *Sci Rep*. **2018**, 8, 1–16.
- [6] J. M. Prendergast, et al. *MAbs* **2017**, 9, 615–627.
- [7] A Diniz. et al, *Chem. Eur. J.*, **2019**, 25, 13945-13955.
- [8] A. Gabba A., et al **2021**, 60, 1327-1336.
- [9] C. D. L. Lima, et. al.; *Chem. Eur. J.* **2021**, 29, 7951-7958.

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT-Portugal) for the funding projects: MGL4Life PTDC/QUI-OUT/2586/2020 (<http://doi.org/10.54499/PTDC/QUI-OUT/2586/2020>), UCIBIO project UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 and i4HB project LA/P/0140/2020). F.M. thanks FCT-Portugal for the CEEC contract CEECINST/00042/2021. The NMR spectrometers are part of the National NMR Facility supported by FCT-Portugal (ROTEIRO/0031/2013- PINFRA/22161/2016, cofinanced by FEDER through COMPETE 2020, POCI and PORL and FCT through PIDDAC). F.M., A.P., P.V. and J.J.B. acknowledge the project HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417-GLYCOTwinning funded by European Commission.